

MANGANESE CONTENT OF INDIAN FOODSTUFFS AND OTHER MATERIALS.

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Manganese contents of a number of vegetable and animal materials have been determined. Rohit fish scales have been found to be richest in manganese content (8.831 mg./100 g. dry) and tender amaranth leaves are richest among vegetable materials. Milk is poor in manganese content.

The importance of manganese in plant nutrition is now recognised. Manganese appears also to be important in animal nutrition. Within certain concentrations manganese appears to stimulate tissue respiration and formation of autotoxin in animals (*cf.* Oettingen, *Physiol Rev.*, 1935, **15**, 175). Kemmerer, Elvejem and Hart (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1931, **92**, 623) found that the addition of traces of manganese to a milk diet had a favourable effect upon the growth of mice. Normal ovulation failed in mice grown on milk supplemented with iron and copper only but the addition of manganese produced normal oestrous cycles. Orent and McCollum (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1931, **92**, 651) found that on manganese-free diets young rats grow normally, females have normal oestrous cycles and bear normal number of youngs but they failed to suckle the youngs. In male rats complete degeneration of the testis occurred with consequent sterility. Keil, Keil and Nelson, (*Amer. J. Physiol.*, 1934, **108**, 215), however, obtained reproduction in the first generation and no reproduction in the second generation of rats on a manganese-free diet.

Manganese thus appears to be an important mineral in animal nutrition and Everson and Daniels (*J. Nutrition*, 1934, **8**, 497) suggest a daily dose of 0.2—0.3 mg. of manganese per kg. of body weight in the case of children. The importance of the knowledge of the distribution of manganese in foodstuffs is, therefore, apparent. No attempt appears to have yet been made to find out manganese distribution in our foodstuffs, although in Europe and America such work has been carried out (*cf.* Oettingen, *loc. cit.*). Boyd and De (*Indian. J. Med. Res.*, 1933, **21**, 109) carried out some spectrographic analysis of foodstuffs and found manganese lines but no quantitative data were given. In the present study the manganese content of a number of Indian foodstuffs and some other materials has been determined. The determinations were made by the method described by Skinner and Peterson (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1930, **88**, 347) with modifications when found

necessary. Two of the items were, in addition, determined by the method of Richards (*Analyst*, 1930, 55, 554). The results are given in the following tables.

TABLE I.

Manganese content of plant materials.

Name.	Scientific name.	Mn content mg./100 g. (dry basis).
Cereals		
Rice, sun-dried, polished	<i>Oryza sativa</i>	1.34
„ parboiled	„	1.06
Wheat	<i>Triticum vulgare</i>	2.07
Pulses		
Green gram	<i>Phaseolus mungo</i>	1.93
Bengal gram	<i>Cicer arietinum</i>	3.00
Vegetables, leafy		
Cabbage	<i>Brassica oleracea capitata</i>	5.69
Amaranthus, tender	<i>Amaranthus gangetica</i>	6.37
„ mature	„	5.86
Vegetables, root		
Carrot	<i>Daucus carota</i>	0.754
Knol khol	<i>Brassica oleracea caulorapa</i>	5.21
Vegetables, other		
Cauliflower	<i>Brassica oleracea botrytes</i>	2.62
Brinjal	<i>Solanum melongena</i>	2.40
Fruits		
Gnava	<i>Psidium guyava</i>	1.59
Chillies, green	<i>Capsicum annum</i>	1.64
Jujuba plum	<i>Zizyphus jujube</i>	0.982
Indian gooseberry	<i>Emblica officinalis</i>	2.90

TABLE II.

Manganese content of animal materials.

Name.	Scientific name.	Manganese content moist tissue.	mg./100 g. dry tissue.
Goat			
Liver		0'338	1'233
Muscle		0'0170	0'073
Blood, whole		0'010*	—
Blood, serum		0'004*	—
Milk		0'0075*	—
Milk, cow's		0'006*	—
Rohit fish, muscle	<i>Labeo rohita</i>	0'0455	'248
Do scale	„	—	8'831
Calbosh fish, muscle	<i>Labeo calbosi</i>	0'0442	0'243
Mrigal fish	„ <i>Cirrhina mrigala</i>	0'0384	'201
Catla fish	„ <i>Catla catla</i>	0'0382	0'211
Chital fish	„ <i>Notopterus chitala</i>	0'0502	0'241

DISCUSSION.

From the above results it will be seen that of the materials investigated amaranthus (*nate sag*) among plant materials and scales of rohit fish among animal materials are richest in manganese content. It is also significant that plant products, which are rich in manganese content, are also generally rich in vitamin C content. Thus amaranth, *brassica oleraceas*, chillies etc., which are rich in vitamin C content are also more or less rich in manganese contents. Indian gooseberry is very rich in vitamin C content and its manganese content is also high. Of the two root vegetables, knol khol and carrot, the former is rich and the latter is very poor in vitamin C content. Their manganese contents are also similarly high and poor, namely 5'21 and 0'754 mg./100 g. respectively. That manganese content of living materials runs almost parallel with their vitamin C content is brought out more clearly from the following table

* per 100 c.c.

which gives the manganese content and vitamin C content (determined titrimetrically with indophenol reagent) of tender and mature amaranth leaves.

TABLE III.

Manganese and vitamin contents of amaranth leaves.

	Mn content mg./100 g. dry.	Vit. C content mg./100 g. moist.
Tender	6.37	151.0
Mature	5.86	140.0

The author holds the opinion that manganese plays an important rôle in the biological synthesis of vitamin C. It has been found that manganese has considerable influence in the vitamin C content of seedlings and the hypothesis has been advanced that manganese is an indispensable link in the mechanism by which plants synthesise vitamin C initially (communicated to the press ; *cf.* also *Nature*, 1938, **141**, 203).

The high manganese content of Rohit fish scales (and probably of other fish scales) should encourage one to investigate the possibility of utilising them in the manufacture of edibles, jelly crystals for example.

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